

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Network Rail

12 – 23 July 2021

Automatic detection of counterfort
drains

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6498538>

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

The Network Rail (NR) railway network is divided among 5 Regions and 14 Routes and covers 36,000 kilometers of track. There are more than 190,000 earthworks within the asset portfolio and over 40,000 are examined every year during manual inspections.

Network Rail's 2014 national aerial survey project collected high resolution ortho-rectified imagery and a fully classified Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) point cloud. As LiDAR can penetrate through the small gaps in vegetation, it can return signals from the ground itself. The point cloud has been processed to remove all vegetation, buildings and other man-made structures to create a digital terrain model (DTM) of the ground surface. The DTM has an accuracy of 5cm vertically, therefore provides a valuable insight into earthworks that, from a photographic perspective, are often obscured by vegetation.

A counterfort drain is a drainage feature on a slope that lowers the groundwater within a slope and reduces the risk of the slope failing. They are often perpendicular to the alignment of the railway but can be diagonal. Counterfort drains are channels that are dug into a slope and are filled with aggregate to allow the controlled seepage of water down a slope towards a manage drainage system.

Earthworks examination, investigation and monitoring do not change the likelihood of failure of the earthworks, but they facilitate the risk-based approach and provide early warning of accelerating deterioration.

By better understanding their assets, National Rail can avoid getting to the point where massive remediations are required. A geospatially accurate and automated method for detecting counterfort drains would improve Network Rail's asset inventory, enable asset engineers to make informed decisions, improve maintenance regimes and ensure compliance with the geospatial standard.

This challenge aimed to automatically detect counterfort drains in the provided aerial photography and digital terrain model (DTM) data. Whilst many drains are not visible in red-green-blue (RGB) images, they are

identifiable in DTM data. The challenge was to build a machine learning model that can detect and segment drains using some combination of the two data modalities.

1.2 Data overview

Network Rail provided 162 tiles of RGB and corresponding DTM data, each tile representing a 500m by 500m area. Geographic information system (GIS) data was also provided of railway track centre lines, as well as property boundary data. Finally, bounding box coordinates for known drain locations on 13 of the tiles were provided by Network Rail, and a those for a further 15 tiles were provided by the challenge PIs.

1.3 Main objectives

The main objectives of this DSG are the following:

- Identify and explore data pre-processing methods using the two image modalities
- Select, train, and evaluate a machine learning model for pixel-wise segmentation
- Post-process the predictive heatmaps to remove false positives and better match the true shapes of detected drains

1.4 Approach

We firstly identified the need to subdivide each image tile into smaller image chips of a computationally feasible size for training. We also explored several pre-processing methods to generate additional forms of data. Several model and pipelines were considered, and we eventually chose a supervised deep learning model, a U-Net architecture. We experimented with a range of learning rates and loss functions to reach optimal convergence. Finally, test image tiles were chipped and passed through the final trained model to generate drain prediction heatmaps.

1.5 Main conclusions

In many cases, drains that are not visible in RGB aerial photographs can still be identified by our U-Net model, thanks to the DTM and additional DTM-generated data. This indicates a multimodal approach is effective and should be explored further.

1.6 Limitations

While we were able to detect many counterfort drains using the multimodal approach, we often did not detect drains that are not perpendicular to the railway tracks. Furthermore, a full exploration of the model hyper-parameter space could not be performed in the time allowed. Finally, the team was unable to complete the post-processing tasks.

A crucial limitation was the amount of data provided for training; in particular, we anticipate that having a much larger and more diverse collection of ground truth bounding boxes for drain locations would greatly increase the model's performance. It would also enable a more thorough evaluation of the model's strengths and weaknesses.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

The multimodal approach taken has shown promising results. We recommend taking this approach further with a deep investigation of hyper-parameters settings to maximise accuracy. A further ablation study on the used data channels should be performed, and the proposed post-processing steps are undertaken to deal with edge cases and reduce false negatives.

2 Introduction and Problem Definition

The Network Rail railway network consists of 36,000 kilometers of track. Surrounding these tracks are more than 190,000 earthworks that support and protect the railway network. One type of such earthwork, a counterfort drain, is a feature on a slope that lowers the groundwater within the slope

to reduce the risk of the slope failing. Near railways, counterfort drains are used to prevent slopes subsiding and causing damage to the tracks or railway stock (as shown in Figure 1). They are channels dug into a slope, typically perpendicular to the track, and filled with aggregate to allow the controlled seepage of water towards a drainage system.

Every year, Network Rail inspects over 40,000 earthworks to ensure they function appropriately. Often, counterfort drains become covered with vegetation making them difficult to access and maintain. In such cases, knowing the precise location of the drain greatly reduces the risks incurred. However, the locations of drains are often recorded as vague approximations. In 2020 Network Rail introduced a geospatial standard stating all assets must be located within 1m of their true location to overcome such issues.

This DSG aims to accurately and precisely locate counterfort drains in Network Rail's portfolio using overhead imagery. While many counterfort drains are visible in orthographic RGB images, others may be covered by vegetation and only visible in a digital terrain model data captured from LiDAR. DTM imagery is not hindered by vegetation and shows a clear view of the terrain. When RGB images are unable to show counterfort drains, DTMs distinguish the difference in height between the drainage channels and surrounding terrain.

Figure 1: Use of counterfort drains to prevent earthwork failures near railways.

Figure 2: Map showing the Settle to Carlisle railway line, and the locations of the DTM and aerial photograph tiles provided by Network Rail

2.1 Data

While Network Rail possesses many datasets, this project focused on orthogonal RGB and DTM imagery captured from LiDAR. These images centre on approximately 80km of railway track and show the full extent of Network Rail's property around the railway. In many cases, land outside of the property boundary is also shown. The images are orthographic and geographically referenced meaning the exact location in space of each pixel is known. Additionally, geographic data was provided as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

2.1.1 RGB data

162 RGB aerial image tiles were provided. Each tile is 12500 by 12500 pixels in size and represents an area of approximately 500m by 500m.

Figure 3: Example tile showing the RGB, DTM and spatial data provided.

Each pixel therefore represents an area of approximately 4cm by 4cm.

2.1.2 DTM data

Like the RGB images, each tile of the DTM data used represents an area of approximately 500m by 500m. Each tile is 2500 by 2500 pixels, meaning that the DTM points captured are spaced approximately 20cm apart.

While the DTM data can identify drains that are hidden in RGB images, the relative differences in elevation between points within a drain compared to points in the surrounding terrain is often small relative to the sharp incline of the terrain in general. To emphasise these relative differences, roughness maps and hillshades were generated that give pronounced indications of where drains are located. These can be seen in Figure 4 and a deeper discussion on their generation is provided in

Section 4.

Figure 4: Each column showing the RGB, DTM, and DTM-generated tiles for each selected location, ordered from left to right of decreasing visibility in DTM imagery.

2.1.3 Location data

GIS data of the railway track centre lines and Network Rail property boundaries were also provided. We used these to restrict the search space for valid counterfort drains in the post-processing step. The ground truth for known counterfort drain locations on 28 tiles were also made available as bounding polygons.

3 Exploring Possible Approaches

We considered several suitable frameworks that fit the project requirements. While combining remote sensing data with RGB imagery seemed promising for drain detection, it also required a model which could accept multiple inputs. We decided to explore the use of a convolutional neural network (CNN), a deep learning neural network.

3.1 CNNs for image analysis

A convolutional neural network (CNN) is a deep neural network that is commonly used in pattern recognition and computer vision [16]. A deep learning model inspired by the animal visual cortex, the CNN is trained on images to recognize spatial features [3, 6].

3.2 Challenges and possible approaches

The input dimensions of a CNN can easily be customized, making it a reasonable choice for our multi-modal input.

Semantic segmentation, or pixel-wise segmentation, is the process of clustering “parts of images together which belong to the same object class” [14]. Surveying the existing literature for possible machine learning approaches for multi-modal inputs narrowed our considerations to three approaches.

3.2.1 Parallel networks

The first approach is multi-modal and multi-model. This framework divides the channels to be processed by parallel networks, and concatenates the outcomes as for a final prediction [10]. Parallel neural networks (PNN) work are trained in parallel, and are joined at inference time to predict the best outcome. One of the advantages of this approach is that each separate network has a potentially simpler task to perform than a single neural network learning all channels simultaneously [5]. Another advantage is that various input channels could be aggregated

based on their importance and hierarchy. A visual depiction of this approach is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Parallel Network Approach.

3.2.2 Expanding the number of inputs

The second approach is to expand the number of input channels to account for the extra channels [11]. This approach, shown in Figure 6, requires adjusting the model architecture and training parameters and is a easily implemented.

3.2.3 Reduction and fusion

A relatively new and promising technique for dealing with multimodal data is called fusion [9, 13, 17]. The fusion of optical images and topographic data is one of the most studied methods in combining satellite images and remote sensing data for landscape classification [17]. The general methodology is shown in Figure 7.

3.3 Our chosen methodology

Considering the time constraints for the challenge and implementation feasibility, we decided to explore the expanding inputs approach. This meant combining multiple modes of input as channels of a single input, all

Figure 6: Expanding the number of inputs channels

Figure 7: Expanding the number of inputs channels

of which are then passed into the neural network. We adapted the first convolutional layer of the chosen U-Net architecture to accept our seven input channels.

4 Data Pre-processing

This section describes the pre-processing performed on both the training and test datasets.

4.1 Training data

Images for training the model were pre-processed via the following steps:

4.1.1 Training tile selection

The training images were generated from the provided tiles with ground truth labels for the position of counterfort drains present. In total, 28 tiles containing bounding boxes surrounding counterfort drains were provided: 13 from Network Rail, and an additional 15 from the challenge PIs. Drain locations on 5 of these tiles were interpreted by both parties; where duplication occurred, one set of interpretations was removed, with Network Rail's interpretations being favoured over the challenge PI's. A further 4 tile interpretations were discounted because they either: (a) contained no drains within National Rail's property boundary, or (b) contained bounding boxes surrounding features that, on further inspection, turned out not to be drains. In all, of the approximately 160 tiles provided in the challenge, only 19 tiles were used to generate training data for the machine learning model.

4.1.2 RGB image down-sampling

The aerial RGB photographs provided were 12500 by 12500 pixels per 500m by 500m tile, whereas the DTM tiles (also 500m by 500m) were 2500 by 2500 pixels. In order to ensure all training images were the same resolution, the aerial photographs were downsampled to 2500 by 2500 pixels using a Python script (`upscale_tifs.py`), provided in section 9.

This downsampling reduced the pixel size of each (photograph) tile by 5 times; pixel values of multiple pixels in the original image were averaged to form larger pixels (as shown in Figure 8). The process of downsampling ultimately led to a loss of information, but also reduced processing time and computational expense.

4.1.3 Attribute map generation

In order to maximize the amount of information extracted from the DTM data, three attribute maps were generated (as shown in Figure 9). These attribute maps therefore acted as an additional three channels to augment the training of the machine learning model.

Figure 8: Example image showing (A) an aerial photograph of an area containing numerous, obvious counterfort drains, (B) a schematic explanation of the downsampling procedure, with pixel values averaged, and (C) the same image as shown in A after downsampling has been conducted.

Roughness Roughness maps demonstrate how ‘rough’ a given area is. They are generated by assigning a value to each pixel of a DTM, according to how different its elevation is compared to its neighbours. Roughness maps were generated in QGIS using the default values¹. See reference [4] to see the details of gdalDEM tool to analyze and visualize digital elevation model.

Alternatively, a script could be written using GDAL in Python to automate this process.

Hillshade Hillshade maps simulate a light shining on a DTM from a given angle and height above the surface. In doing so, slopes facing towards the simulated light appear lighter (they are illuminated), whereas slopes facing away from the simulated light appear darker (they are in shadow). This allows the identification of more subtle features than can be identified using elevation data alone. As most of the counterfort drains in the tiles used to generate the training images are perpendicular to the railway, the azimuth (direction) of the simulated light was track-parallel.

¹ `gdalDEM roughness / input_folder/input_file.tif /output_folder/output_file.tif -of GTiff -b 1`

Figure 9: Example DTM tile showing the attributes that were generated from each tile.

The hillshade maps used herein were generated automatically using a Python script (`automated_hillshades.ipynb`), provided in section 9.

The azimuth of the simulated light (track-parallel) was calculated by finding the two points at which the railway centreline (provided as a polyline by Network Rail) intersects with the boundary of the DTM tile. The orientation of a straight line connecting the two intersection points provides the azimuth of the simulated light (as shown in Figure 10B). To ensure the illumination of as many features as possible two hillshade maps were generated from each tile: Hillshade A is generated using simulated light directed 'down track' (away from London; roughly north; Figure 10C) Hillshade B is generated using simulated light directed 'up track' (toward London; roughly south; Figure 10D)

Figure 10: Example tile showing the process of generating hillshade A and hillshade B, and the calculation of the light azimuth

4.1.4 Boundary polygon editing

While the boundary polygons provided each contained a single drain, in many cases these polygons were broad boxes that contained the drain itself in addition to a significant amount of surrounding ground. Editing of these bounding polygons to encompass only pixels interpreted to be part of drains was conducted in QGIS (as shown in Figure 11), with the view to improve the accuracy of the masks used to train the machine learning model.

4.1.5 Chipping

Training images containing drains, and others containing no drains were generated using a 'chipping' process. 25.6m by 25.6m images ('chips') were generated with a random distribution across each training tile (as shown in Figure 12). Each chip is classified according to whether or not it contains a drain. To ensure a consistent ratio of chips containing drains,

Figure 11: Example image showing the procedure of editing the boundary polygons to contain only areas interpreted as drains.

to chips devoid of drains, more drain-containing chips were generated in tiles that contained more drains, as identified by the boundary polygons. Chipping was conducted automatically using a Python script (`generate_training_data.ipynb`), provided in section 9.

4.2 Testing data

Similar steps for pre-processing the training data were used to pre-process the testing data, with the exception of 'training tile selection', and 'polygon editing', which are not applicable to the testing data. The downsampling of aerial photographs and the production of roughness and hillshade maps were conducted using the same methods as for the training data. However, the chipping methodology for the testing data differed slightly. A grid of 25.6m x 25.6m chips was generated (as shown in Figure 13). Each chip overlaps its neighbours on all sides by 12.8 (half), in turn generating very dense coverage over the tile. As data testing was only conducted within Network Rail's property boundary, if a chip's centre point fell outside of the property boundary, it was not used for testing. Chipping of the tiles used in the testing data was conducted automatically using a Python script (`generate_testing_data.ipynb`), provided in section 9.

Figure 12: Example tile showing the location of sampled chips for training

5 Machine Learning for Drain Detection

5.1 Approach

Deep learning methods have proven successful in the image domain for object detection and localization problems, and have potential to be suitable for the problem of automatic detection of counterfort drains. CNNs are deep learning-based models inspired by the connectivity patterns found in neurons in the animal visual cortex. Model inputs in many instances of object detection and localization tasks are colour or gray-scale images with either 3 or 1 channels respectively. In our problem, due to the occlusion present in some data and the multiple modes of imagery available, we have adjusted our CNN to process a 7-channel input. As mentioned in Subsection 3.3, we used a stacking approach for the channels of the image. Each image is composed of a

Figure 13: Example tile showing the location of sampled chips for testing

tensor of dimensions $7 \times 128 \times 128$ pixels.

5.2 Hyper-parameters

5.2.1 Choice of optimizer

At its core, a deep learning algorithm is an optimization algorithm that aims to minimize an objective function (usually known as "loss"). Optimizers are criteria for reducing the training loss. We tried two commonly used variations of gradient descent.

- **Stochastic gradient descent:** an iterative method for optimization which computes, at each iteration, the gradients of a sub-sampling of the training data rather than on the entire set; a stochastic approximation of gradient descent.

- **Adam:** a combination of two other popular adaptive learning rate optimizers, adapting the learning rate based on exponential moving average of the gradients [7].

5.2.2 Choice of learning rate

The learning rate is a parameter for deep learning optimizers that determines the step size at each iteration while moving toward the minimum of a loss function. A careful search for a good learning rate is crucial for ensuring convergence and preventing overfitting of the model on the training data. The learning rate also sometimes requires a scheduler to manually or automatically adapt the step size based on certain criteria, to ensure convergence.

5.2.3 Choice of loss function

Loss functions, as described in previous sections, are metrics that quantify the prediction error of a neural network during training. The optimizer usually takes steps in directions that will minimize the loss function. We experimented with four different loss functions which had significant impact on the output predictions.

- **Dice Coefficient:** a pixel segmentation metric also usable as a loss function, measuring the the union of the predicted mask and true mask proportionate to the mask region size.
- **Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE):** a binary classification metric based on the log of corrected predicted probabilities for each pixel.
- **Binary Cross-Entropy with Dice:** This loss combines Dice loss with the standard binary cross-entropy (BCE) loss that is generally the default for segmentation models. Combining the two methods allows for some diversity in the loss, while benefitting from the stability of BCE.
- **BCE with logits:** If the dataset is imbalanced, then BCE with logits loss is used to establish stable training. This loss combines a Sigmoid layer and the BCE Loss in one single class. This version is more numerically stable than using a plain Sigmoid followed by a

BCE Loss as, by combining the operations into one layer, we take advantage of the log-sum-exp trick for numerical stability [1].

5.2.4 Choice of activation function

Activation functions are tied to neurons at different layers of the deep neural network, that determine whether that particular neuron should be activated or not. Choice of activation functions also impacts the quality of training. We considered two different activation functions.

- **ReLU:** The rectified linear activation function (ReLU) is a piecewise linear function that will output the input directly if it is positive, otherwise, it will output zero. ReLU is based on the principle that models are easier to optimize if their behavior is closer to linear.
- **LeakyReLU:** Leaky ReLU solves the “dying ReLU” problem. Instead of the function being zero when $x < 0$, a leaky ReLU will instead have a small negative slope (of 0.01, or so). That is, the function computes:

$$f(x) = 1(x < 0)(\alpha x) + 1(x \geq 0)(x), \quad (1)$$

where α is a small constant. While observed in literature that Leaky ReLU is more feasible for datasets with such a high variations in pixel values at the same spatial location [2], we were unable to complete tests using LeakyReLU and leave this to future work.

5.3 Training and testing methodology

We selected a tested an encoder-decoder architecture called the U-Net, derived from the fully convolutional networks proposed by Long et al. [8]. It was developed by Ronneberger et al. [12] for biomedical image segmentation and has been widely adopted in other applications, including building segmentation in aerial images [15].²

To train our network, we took a supervised learning approach using the labelled drains in the training images, converted into a raster mask. Of

²We used the U-Net open source implementation available at <https://www.kaggle.com/balraj98/unet-with-pretrained-resnet50-encoder-pytorch/output>.

the tiles provided, 19 of them had labelled drains in them. These were chipped, and we obtained a total of $n = 893$ chips with at least one drain partially visible in the chip and 3,495 with no drains present. These chips were generated at random, so given the sparsity of drains compared to regular terrain in the imagery, it is to be expected that there are fewer chips with a drain present. However, having two unbalanced classes of examples can make it more difficult for the model to converge. While one potential way to deal with the problem would be to incorporate class weighting into the loss function, we instead chose to selectively reduce the number of chips with no drains in them and kept n , resulting in two balanced classes.

The set of $2n$ chips was split into set of 90% for training and 10% for validation. We also augmented each image chip by randomly applying one or more of the following transformations: a 90° rotation, a horizontal flip, or a vertical flip. As is typically done for regularization purposes and more efficient training, we trained the network using batches of 16 images. We were unable to experiment with larger batch sizes due to hardware constraints.

6 Results and Evaluation

In this section, we present the results of detailed experimentation of the U-Net architecture for identifying counterfort drains.

Due to the limited amount of labelled training data available for training, the validation set was used for hyper-parameter tuning as well as for evaluation. While not optimal, these potentially optimistic results on the prototype model clearly indicate that given more data, and with independent validation and testing sets, a model could reach comparable performance if not better. The tuned model was tested on previously unseen chips from a separate DTM with visually comparable results, although these are not presented in this report.

6.1 Quantitative evaluation

As shown in table 6.2, all tested experiments are summarized with different choices of optimizer, loss function and learning rate. It can be seen from Table 6.2 that the U-Net model failed to converge for Dice loss functions and SGD optimizers with different choices of learning rates. The performance and convergence behavior of the model suggests that it performed very well with a BCE-logits loss function and Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-4} .

Figure 17 shows the interactive convergence behaviour of model for different loss functions. Model validation accuracy oscillates between 0.83 – 0.86 for Dice-BCE loss function. It performed very well for BCE-logits loss function but with learning rate 7×10^{-5} , model validation loss starts increasing after epoch 40. Overall, the model shows best convergence behaviour for BCE-logits loss with a learning rate of 10^{-4} .

6.2 Qualitative evaluation

Visual evaluation of the prediction heatmaps confirms that the model can locate counterfort drains, placing stronger confidence towards the centerline of each drain and decreasing for positions further away from it. This indicates that the model has learned to detect textural features associated with the drains.

In some cases, as shown in the top row of images in Figure 15, the model can locate drains not visible on the RGB imagery, a strong confirmation that the channel stacking technique incorporating various forms of the DTM data gives the model critical information to learn from. Row 2 of Figure 15 shows that stone walls are sometimes mistaken for drains, an error which could be dealt with by increasing training data (specifically including more samples with stone walls) or post-processing; while row 3 of Figure 14 is a counterexample of a stone wall correctly undetected.

Figure 14: Results with DiceBCE

7 Post-processing

The output of the trained model is a pixel-wise labelling, or binary mask, for each of the chips for the whole dataset. These image segmentations indicate the model's prediction of what is drain versus not drain. In the post-processing stage, we can use tools in Python's Raster IO library to convert these images back into labelled points that are geospatially referenced. By finding connected components in space of points labelled as drains, the estimated locations and shapes of drains can be found and exported as a geospatial dataset (e.g. in GeoJSON or Shapefile format), easily usable by Network Rail in their existing system.

Several observations guide our post-processing considerations. Firstly, we know that counterfort drains are typically straight channels dug into soil. Furthermore, drains are cut into slopes. Therefore, any prospective drain polygons that are not approximately straight can be ignored as false positives. Furthermore, drains that are close together and have

Figure 15: Results with BCELogits

approximately the same median lines may be joined by removing the gap that separates them.

The GIS meta data could be used to reduce false positives identified outside Network Rail boundaries, and to encourage consideration of detections non-perpendicular to the track at key locations such as on top of tunnel entrances, for edge-case scenarios.

Finally, each prospective drain polygon can be replaced by a single median line through its centre that describes the likely path of that counterfort drain. If drains are known to be of approximately the same standard width, a rectangle of that standard width can be created around that centre line. This will give a straight and rectangular polygon in the final polygon Shapefile where a drain is suspected to be.

Whilst the challenge team was unable to complete these post-processing steps, we believe this process will remove the majority of false positives from the model output. Furthermore, this post-processing will smooth the

Figure 16: More results with BCELogits

polygons of the detected drains and likely result in a more accurate and useful dataset.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

8.1 Conclusion

In many locations, counterfort drains can be hard to distinguish from RGB imagery or un-processed DTM imagery alone. Factors such as vegetation, lighting, and relative elevations can prevent methods focusing on single-modal pattern recognition from detecting drains accurately. However, the multi-modal approach of combining RGB with DTM and DTM-generated data has been shown through this DSG challenge to greatly improve the accuracy of intelligent counterfort drain detection models.

Whilst this project has shown promising results, combining multiple modalities of data is still an active area of research. Further research on

Optimizer	Loss	LR	Validation-IoU	Summary
Adam	Dice	10^{-2}	≈ 0	Did not converge
Adam	Dice	10^{-3}	0.81	Produced all-black masks
Adam	Dice-BCE	10^{-4}	0.83-0.86 (Oscillating)	Converged, but results worse compared to BCELogits
Adam	BCE-Logits	3×10^{-4}	0.85	Overfit before converging
Adam	BCE-Logits	10^{-4}	0.86	Best convergence, overfit after reaching a low validation loss
Adam	BCE-Logits	7×10^{-5}	0.84	Took longer to converge, validation loss higher than with 10^{-4}
SGD	Dice	10^{-2}	0.01	A scheduler could not be used, failed to converge entirely
SGD	Dice	10^{-3}	0.01	A scheduler could not be used, failed to converge entirely

Table 1: Summary of the experiments tested

modelling techniques for multi-modal data will likely improve the accuracy of drain identification. Furthermore, as deep neural networks are known to excel with more data, we strongly expect that the addition of more labelled data for training will improve our model’s performance. This DSG was also limited by the availability of time and hardware resources (GPUs) for model training; with more data and resources, a wider range of hyper-parameters can be tested. Finally, the team was unable to complete the intended post-processing of the model output. We anticipate that the completion of the steps described in Section 7 will result in useful and accurate outputs.

8.2 Future Work

We have identified the following areas of future work.

In Section 6.2, drains lying perpendicular to railway tracks were identified with a higher accuracy than those lying at other angles. We suggest this may be caused by their clearer identification in the hillshade data. Thus, generating a range of hillshades at regular intervals (e.g. 10° increments) may improve the identification of other drains. Furthermore, upsampling the DTM data rather than downsampling the RGB data will increase the

Figure 17: Comparison of the convergence for different experiments

amount of information used by the machine learning models, and this may also effect the final model performance.

Further investigations into other model architectures proposed in literature may increase the accuracy of drain identification. Furthermore, custom designed architectures specifically for RGB, DTM and the derived data may be beneficial. Finally, an ablation study should be performed to identify the contributions of each channel.

9 Code resources

1. Base code reference: <https://www.kaggle.com/balraj98/unet-with-pretrained-resnet50-encoder-pytorch/output>
2. https://github.com/thesidjway/network-rail-dsg/tree/master/scripts/upscale_tifs.py
3. https://github.com/thesidjway/network-rail-dsg/blob/master/scripts/automated_hillshades.ipynb
4. https://github.com/thesidjway/network-rail-dsg/tree/master/scripts/generate_training_data.ipynb
5. https://github.com/thesidjway/network-rail-dsg/tree/master/scripts/generate_testing_data.ipynb

10 Team members

Siddharth Jha is the technical lead at Preimage AI, a drone photogrammetry startup. He contributed to this project by co-writing the pre-processing and deep learning algorithms, and was also involved in the conceptualization and testing of the approach.

Rodrigo Leal-Cervantes is a DPhil student in Mathematics at the University of Oxford. He contributed to this project by writing the code for upsampling or downsampling the images and co-developing the deep-learning methods. He was also involved in the conceptualization and testing of the approach.

Sara Richards is a PhD candidate at York University. Her research focuses on computational social science and combining data science with social data studies. She contributed to this project by researching and narrowing down machine learning methods and collaborating in the implementation of the deep learning approach.

Liam Steadman is a data and research engineer at MyNestBox, and recently completed his PhD in Computer Science at the University of Warwick. He contributed to this project as its facilitator by working with the principle investigators and working on the pre-processing steps.

Daniel Tek is a PhD student in Marine Sedimentology at the University of Leeds. He contributed to this project by planning and executing some of the pre-processing steps, generating figures, and writing some of the report.

Rebecca Stone is a PhD student in Computer Science at the University of Leeds, interested in Bayesian deep learning and passionate about teaching. She contributed to the project as a co-principle investigator by working with Network Rail to formulate the challenge, and by providing general support to the team.

Usman Nazir is a split-site PhD student in Computer Science at the University of Leeds. He is passionate for building scalable machine learning systems and algorithms to learn socio-economic indicators from remote sensing data at large-scale. He contributed to the project as a Co-Principle Investigator by working with Network Rail to formulate the

challenge and annotate the RGB images using LabelMe annotation tool, and by providing support to the team in hyper-parameters tuning.

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